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СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1.	Абдухалик-Заде Г.А. ПРОФИЛАКТИКА АНЕМИИ НЕДОНОШЕННЫХ НА АМБУЛАТОРНОМ ЭТАПЕ.....	6
2.	Ashurova M. J.,Garifulina L. M. SAMARQAND VILOYATIDAGI SEMIZLIGI BOR BOLALARDA VITAMIN D STATUSINI BAHOLASH.....	9
3.	Begmatov J.A., Goyibov S. S. IMPROVEMENTS AFTER SURGICAL ANESTHESIA IN ELDERLY AND OLD AGE PATIENTS IN THE INTERVENTION OF THE HIP JOINT.....	13
4.	Бойқўзиев Ҳ.Х., Джуракулов Б. И. ЦИТОКИНЛАР ВА НЕЙРОИММУНОЭНДОКРИН АЛОҚАЛАР.....	16
5.	Гайбуллаев Ж. Ш. ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ЛЕЧЕБНОЙ ТАКТИКИ ПРИ ОСТРОМ ОБСТРУКТИВНОМ БРОНХИТЕ У ДЕТЕЙ С..... МИОКАРДИТАМИ	20
6.	Garifulina L. M., Kholmuradova Z.E., Kudratova G. N. RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION AND OBESITY IN CHILDREN IN ACCORDANCE WITH PERINATAL METABOLISM PROGRAMMING.....	23
7.	Garifulina L.M., Kholmuradova Z. E., Qodirova Sh. S. INDICATORS OF THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF OBESITY AND ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION.....	27
8.	Гойибов С. С., Нематуллоев Т. К. ДЕТЕРМИНАНТЫ ПЕРИОПЕРАЦИОННЫХ ИСХОДОВ В КОЛОРЕКТАЛЬНОЙ ХИРУРГИИ: РОЛЬ КОМОРБИДНОСТИ И ЗАСТОЙНОЙ СЕРДЕЧНОЙ НЕДОСТАТОЧНОСТИ.....	30
9.	Даминов Ф.А. КЕКСА БЕМОРЛАРДА КАТТА МАЙДОНЛИ КУЙИШЛАРДА СТРЕСС ЯРАЛАРИННГ УЧРАШ ЧАСТОТАСИ ВА УЛАРИНГ АСОРАТЛАРИНИНГ УЗИГА ХОСЛИГИ.....	33
10.	Zakirova B.I., Xusainova Sh. K. OPTIMIZATION OF IRRITANT INTESTINAL SYNDROME THERAPY.....	37
11.	Ishkabalova G.Dj., Rahmonqulov Sh. BOLALARDA BUYRAKLARNING FUNKSIONAL ZAXIRASINING DIZMETABOLIK NEFROPATIYALARDA O'ZGARISHI.....	40
12.	Quldashev S.F., Normakhmatov B.B. EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PRETRACHEAL LYMPHOTROPIC ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY IN CHRONIC LUNG DISEASES IN CHILDREN.....	43
13.	Nabieva Sh. M., INTENSIVE CARE IN NEONATAL RESUSCITATION.....	45
14.	Наврүзова Ш. И., Каримов Р. К. ИММУНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИНДИКАТОРЫ ОСЛОЖНЕНИЙ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКИХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ КИШЕЧНИКА У ДЕТЕЙ.....	48
15.	Нормаматов Б.П., Усмонова Н.У. ЭКСТРАКОРПОРАЛЬНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ХОЛЕМИЧЕСКОЙ ИНТОКСИКАЦИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ ГНОЙНЫМ ХОЛАНГИТОМ.....	53
16.	Нормахматов Б.Б., Кулдашев С.Ф. СОСТОЯНИЕ ПОЛОВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ МАЛЬЧИКОВ ПРИ БРОНХИАЛЬНОЙ АСТМЕ.....	57
17.	Рахманов К. Э. АНАЛИЗ РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ РАДИКАЛЬНОЙ ЭХИНОКОККЭКТОМИИ ИЗ ПЕЧЕНИ.....	60

18.	Xodjayeva S.A., Kayumova Sh. Sh. LYABLIQZNING O'IV BILAN KASALLANGAN BEMORLARDA KLINIK VA LABORATOR XUSUSIYATLARI.....	65
19.	Шарипов Р.Х., Расулова Н.А. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПЕРЕКИСНОГО ОКИСЛЕНИЯ ЛИПИДОВ У ДЕТЕЙ С ПЕРИНАТАЛЬНЫМИ ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЯМИ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ.....	69
20.	Шарипов Р. Х., Расулова Н.А., Расулов А. С. ОЦЕНКА ФАКТОРОВ РАЗВИТИЯ РАХИТА И ПОСЛЕДСТВИЙ ПЕРИНАТАЛЬНОГО ПОВРЕЖДЕНИЯ НЕРВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА.....	73
21.	Шеховцов С. А. ВЛИЯНИЯ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ПОДПороГОВЫХ МОЩНОСТЕЙ ДИОДНОГО ЛАЗЕРА НА ФУНКЦИЮ ЗАПИРАТЕЛЬНОГО АППАРАТА ПРЯМОЙ КИШКИ ПРИ ВЫПОЛНЕНИИ ЛАЗЕРНОЙ ОБЛИТЕРАЦИИ ПРЯМОКИШЕЧНЫХ СВИЩЕЙ ПО ТЕХНОЛОГИИ FiLAC.....	78
22.	Shodikulova G. Z.,Samatov D.K.,Mirzayev O.V., VoxidovJ.J. OSHQOZON ICHAK TRAKTI YUQORI QISMI PATOLOGİYASI BO'LGAN BEMORLARDA BIRIKTIRUVCHI TO'QIMA DIPLAZIYASI KECISHINING KLINIK-LABORATOR XUSUSIYATLARI.....	81

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ЖУРНАЛ ГЕПАТО-ГАСТРОЭНТЕРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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INTENSIVE CARE IN NEONATAL RESUSCITATION

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ANNOTATION

The main direction of the neonatology service is medical and diagnostic assistance. The training of highly qualified specialists, the effective organization of neonatal services and the availability of modern equipment make it possible to qualitatively help critically ill newborn children. The purpose of the study: to analyze the work of the department of intensive care and neonatal resuscitation of the Samarkand regional multidisciplinary Center for the period from 2017 to 2020. The research material was the annual reporting data of this department for 2017-2020. During the period from 2017 to 2020, 3666 newborns were admitted to the department, of which 589 (16%) and 3074 (84%) were admitted to the surgical department for somatic disease. Highly qualified doctors, good diagnostics ensured timely resuscitation, provide respiratory support for newborns, correct hemodynamic disorders, infusion therapy for newborns.

But despite the intensive therapy, neonatal mortality averages 10%, which poses new challenges for us to improve neonatal care. Thus, intensive care in neonatal resuscitation is one of the main links in the provision of medical care to newborns, which requires our doctors to have a high level of knowledge, the use of modern diagnostic methods, and treatment in accordance with state protocols.

Keywords: infusion, neonatology, resuscitation, therapy, newborn.

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NEONATAL REANIMATSIYADA INTENSIV TERAPIYA

ANNOTASIYA

Neonatologik xizmatning asosiy yo'nalishi tibbiy va diagnostik yordamdir. Yuqori malakali mutaxassislarini tayyorlash, neonatal xizmatni samarali tashkil etish va zamonaviy jihozlarning mavjudligi tanqidiy kasal yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarga sifatli yordam beradi. Tadqiqotning maqsadi: Samarqand viloyati ko'p tarmoqli markazining 2017 yildan 2020 yilgacha bo'lgan davrda neonatal intensiv terapiya va reanimatsiya bo'limi ishini tahlil qilish. Tadqiqot materiallari ushbu bo'limning 2017-2020 yillardagi yillik hisobot ma'lumotlari edi. 2017 yildan 2020 yilgacha bo'lgan davrda bo'limga 3666 ta yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq kelib tushdi, ulardan 589 tasi (16%) va 3074 tasi (84%) somatik kasalliklar bo'yicha jarrohlik bo'limiga keldi. Yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarning 3123 (85%) Samarqand viloyati tumanlaridan, 537 (15%) Samarqand shahridan va 635 (17.3%) boshqa viloyatlardan kelgan. Shifokorlarning yuqori malakasi, yaxshi tashxis reanimatsiya tadbirlarini o'z vaqtida o'tkazishni, yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarni nafas olish uchun qo'llab-quvvatlashni, gemodinamik kasalliklarni tuzatishni va yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarni infuzion davolashni ta'minladi.

Ammo intensiv terapiyaga qaramay, neonatal o'lim o'rtacha 10% ni tashkil qiladi, bu bizga neonatal yordamni yaxshilash uchun yangi muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Shunday qilib, neonatal reanimatsiyada intensiv terapiya yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarga tibbiy yordam ko'rsatishning asosiy bo'g'inlaridan biri bo'lib, bu bizdan shifokorlardan yuqori darajadagi bilimlarni, zamonaviy diagnostika usullaridan foydalanishni, davlat protokollariga mos keladigan davolanishni talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: infuzion, neonatologiya, reanimatsiya, terapiya, yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloq.

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ИНТЕНСИВНАЯ ТЕРАПИЯ В НЕОНАТАЛЬНОЙ РЕАНИМАЦИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Основным направлением неонатологической службы является лечебно-диагностическая помощь. Подготовка специалистов высокой квалификации, эффективная организация неонатальной службы и доступность современной аппаратуры позволяют качественно помочь критически больным новорожденным детям. Цель исследования: провести анализ работы отделения интенсивной терапии и реанимации новорожденных Самаркандского областного многопрофильного центра за период с 2017 по 2020 годы. Материалом исследования были

годовые отчетные данные данного отделения за 2017-2020 годы. За период с 2017 по 2020 гг. в отделение поступило новорожденных 3666 новорожденного из которых в хирургическое отделение поступили 589 (16%) и 3074 (84%) по соматическим заболеваниям. 3123 (85%) новорожденных поступили с районов Самаркандской области ,537 (15 %) с города Самарканда и 635 (17.3%) с других областей. Высокая квалификация врачей, хорошая диагностика обеспечивала своевременно провести реанимационные мероприятия, оказать респираторную поддержку новорожденных, провести коррекцию гемодинамических нарушений, инфузионную терапию новорожденных.

Но несмотря на проведенную интенсивную терапию, неонатальная смертность в среднем составляет 10 %, что ставит перед нами новые задачи по улучшению неонатальной помощи. Таким образом, интенсивная терапия в неонатальной реанимации –одна из главных звеньев оказания медицинской помощи новорожденным, которая требует от нас врачей высокий уровень знаний, использование современных методов диагностики, проведения лечения, соответствующих государственным протоколам.

Ключевые слова: инфузия, неонатология, реанимация, терапия, новорожденный.

The relevance of research. Over the past two decades, a special direction in perinatology has appeared — intensive therapy of newborns, which provides for a complex of therapeutic measures at the birth of a child with oxygen deficiency (asphyxia), aimed at restoring cardiac activity, respiration, blood flow, metabolism in all vital organs (1,5,9). Neonatology — It consists in caring for newborns from the first day to 40 days of life, especially those who were born prematurely, as well as with the detection, diagnosis and treatment of specific diseases of this age group, as well as the preservation of life and care for prematurely born newborns. Intensive development of science and technology contributed to a deeper study and understanding of the pathophysiology of premature infants, which contributed to the active nursing of children with extremely low body weight up to 500 grams (4,6,8) Despite the obvious progress in medical science, infant mortality in the country remains high. Neonatology, as one of the young and promising areas in medicine, expands its capabilities according to the requirements of the time and sets new tasks for itself. The improvement of neonatology medical care is the most important factor in reducing mortality and disability of newborn children. The main direction of the neonatology service is medical and diagnostic assistance (2,3,7). The training of highly qualified specialists, the effective organization of neonatal services and the availability of modern equipment make it possible to qualitatively help critically ill newborn children. Taking into account the urgency of this problem, we were tasked with learning how effectively intensive care is carried out in the intensive care unit and neonatal intensive care unit of the Samarkand regional Multidisciplinary Center.

The purpose of the research: to analyze the work of the department of intensive care and neonatal resuscitation of the Samarkand regional multidisciplinary Center for the period from 2017 to 2020.

Research materials: The study was conducted in the Samarkand Regional Multidisciplinary Center in the neonatal intensive care and

intensive care unit. The research material was the annual reporting data of this department for 2017-2020.

Results and discussion: in 2017, in the city of Samarkand in the regional multidisciplinary center, a neonatal intensive care and resuscitation department was established, which consists of a newborn department with 6 beds and a newborn surgery department with 3 beds. The neonatal intensive care unit is ready to act promptly at any time, it is equipped with all the necessary equipment to provide rapid resuscitation of a newborn:

- ventilators (Artificial lung ventilation), which regulate all parameters of the newborn's respiratory system;
 - CPAP devices that generate positive pressure at the end of exhalation;
 - 4 incubators for premature babies that regulate the temperature and humidity of the environment;
 - 6 resuscitation tables with irradiating heat regulating the temperature of the newborn's body;
 - a mobile ultrasound device that allows you to do ultrasonography, neurosonography, ultrasound Doppler at the patient's bed, in the case when the newborn is not transportable;
 - X-ray machine;
 - Echocardiogram device.

Consulting and medical care of a neonatologist and a pediatric surgeon includes:

- Assessment of the newborn's health status;
- Diagnosis and treatment of acute diseases;
- Monitoring the growth and normal development of the newborn;
- Advice on breastfeeding and recommendations on mixed and artificial feeding of a newborn baby;
- Prevention of diseases (vaccination according to the neonatal period);
- Constant monitoring of a newborn in need of intensive care.

THE STRUCTURE OF MORBIDITY OF NEWBORNS

During the period from 2017 to 2020, 3666 newborns were admitted to the department, of which 589 (16%) and 3074 (84%) were admitted to the surgical department for somatic diseases. 3123 (85%) newborns were admitted from the districts of the Samarkand region, 537 (15%) from the city of Samarkand and 635 (17.3%) from other areas. Most of the newborns were hospitalized from maternity complexes in the city of Samarkand. The most frequent transfers from maternity hospital No.2 454(71%). The smallest number of transfers from the perinatal center is 42(7%). The age of newborns at admission was 19%(696) on the first day, 2 days 19% (696), 3 days 8% (293), 4 days 7%(256), 4-10 days 19%(696), 11-30 days 19%(696), 1 month 8% (293). According to nosology, intrauterine infections, damage to the central nervous system, respiratory disorders syndromes, congenital malformations, surgical diseases occupy a leading place. Risk factors that led to the development of the pathological condition of the newborn mother's disease are severe forms of anemia, SARS infections, chronic and acute respiratory diseases, inflammatory diseases of the urinary system, frequent diseases of acute respiratory viral infections, gestosis, hereditary diseases, close related marriages.

Perinatal mortality for the periods from 2017 to 2020 averaged 10%.

According to the gestation period among the deceased newborns, full-term infants made up 51% and premature infants 49%. Among premature infants with low body weight there were 49%, with very low body weight 35% and with extremely low body weight 16%.

The cause of death was brain edema-7%, DIC syndrome -30%, acute renal failure -26%, shock - 7%, acute heart failure -30%. The mortality rate from surgical pathology was 34%. In this structure, intestinal obstruction is in the first place and is 38%, esophageal atresia -26%, diaphragmatic hernia -12%, pylorostenosis-12%, necrotic enterocolitis- 6%, congenital malformations - 6%.

Mortality, depending on the place of admission, was 64% among newborns admitted from maternity hospitals and 36% from home. Pathoanatomic autopsy was performed in 82% of cases. High qualification of doctors, good diagnostics ensured timely resuscitation, respiratory support for newborns, correction of hemodynamic disorders, infusion therapy of newborns. Knowledge of the peculiarities of care and intensive care in children with extremely low body weight contributed to the nursing of children from this group. Special attention was paid to the psychological state of the parents of newborn children. Mothers received reliable information, participated as much as possible in the care of babies, providing breast milk, maintained compliance with the thermal regime, the "kangaroo" method was widely used. The close contact between the sick newborn and his parents, as well as the friendly attitude of the medical staff, had a very positive effect on the health of the babies. But despite the intensive therapy, neonatal mortality averages 10%, which poses new challenges for improving neonatal care.

This is primarily: - professional development of doctors, nurses; - adoption of experience in this field in the leading medical institutions of our country and abroad; - purchase of modern diagnostic equipment, - improvement of the conditions of stay of newborns corresponding to European standards.

During their stay in the hospital, newborns undergo a large number of manipulations and procedures, most of which are quite painful. Adequate analgesia and pain prevention during manipulations and procedures can reduce the discomfort of the child, improve the tolerance of medical manipulations and care procedures.

Conclusions. Thus, intensive care in neonatal intensive care is one of the main links in the provision of medical care to newborns, which requires a high level of knowledge from our doctors, the use of modern diagnostic methods, and treatment that comply with state protocols.

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